

The Coupling Constants Series – Net Curvature versus Spin – 8T

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Abstract:

The paper is emphasizing the difference between the representations of the primordial coupling constants series. in the first representation we analyze via distinct elements, which are net variations/curvature, separate entities. In the spin representation, we either have matter of half integer spin, or Bosons integer spin. This idea yielded the particle wave duality.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M , given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

Up until now, reader is probably familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. **From here** on out, we have a completely **new paper**. This is the first representation of the primordial, discrete amount of net curvature on the manifold. It is a detailed representation as we have leptons, Bosons as separate entities. This does not exist in spin representation of the primordial, and that is precisely how we derived the particle wave duality, due to spin variation. In spin representation, we used the prime critical line. That is the transformation for matter:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right]$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right]$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2}\right]$$

The only thing we care about in this representation is the prime critical line. Matter is associated with one-half, while Boson configuration is associated with one. The spin representation ignore the lepton and regard all the coupling as a spin compass. We do not make a clear cutting classification to particles in this representation. For Bosons:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_1 + 1$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + 1$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2}\right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_3 + 1$$

The key point, despite the spin representation is including matter in its coupling term, we don't care about this, we regard this whole term as spin one, and therefore only to bosons. That is in contrast to the net curvature representation that makes a difference among each element in the coupling term. From spin representation it was quite simple to derive the particle wave duality for Bosons. In particular the particle wave duality is a result of total spin variation by half unit, caused by additional Boson, hitting the original Boson.

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma + \gamma \rightarrow 2N_2 + \frac{3}{2}$$

In spin representation, we have one entity, the total spin of the element, either Fermionic or Bosonic. The photon before measurement had spin one, now we measured it and it varied to one-half, no longer bosonic spin. That was mentioned in the 8T thesis. However, it is important to emphasize the difference among the representations. In net curvature representation, we analyze each element separately, while in spin representation we care only about the total of elements in the prime critical line. The $\left[2N + \frac{1}{2}\right]$ is matter, $2N_3 + 1$ is for Bosons.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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